

LIMIT REFERENCE POINTS AND WILD SALMON POLICY RAPID STATUS SUMMARY: YUKON CHINOOK and PORCUPINE CHINOOK STOCK MANAGEMENT UNITS

Executive Summary

There are 12 Chinook Conservation Units (CUs) in the Yukon, belonging to two Stock Management Units (SMU) – Yukon Chinook SMU and Porcupine Chinook SMU.

- ❖ The **Yukon Chinook SMU** contains nine CUs, and they are designated as 5 *Red* and 4 *Amber*, placing this SMU below its CU-status based Limit Reference Point (LRP) in terms of the Wild Salmon Policy (WSP) status assessment.
- ❖ The **Porcupine Chinook SMU** contains three CUs, and they are designated as 2 *Red* and 1 *Data Deficient*, placing this SMU below its LRP in terms of the WSP status assessment.

The **Yukon River-Teslin Headwaters CU** was assessed as *Red* with *Medium* confidence. The recent generational average of an expanded tributary aerial survey index is 20% of the long-term average (Node 17) (Figures 2-3; Table 5). The WSP rapid status assessment is not available for 2012–2023 due to gaps in aerial survey data, however it was assigned *Red* in the preceding years, from 2009–2011. The long-term trend metric is also *Red* for 2024, and leading into the 2012–2023 gap, this metric downgraded from *Green* to *Amber*. Since 2024 is the only year with a defined WSP rapid status since 2011, subsequent year’s rapid status assessment should be interpreted conservatively if improvements in status are detected.

The **Upper Yukon River CU** was assessed as *Red* with *Medium* confidence. The recent generational average spawner abundance falls below the *absolute abundance* lower thresholds (1,500) (Node 3) (Figures 4-5; Table 6). The WSP rapid status assessment of this CU is based upon a short time series, therefore other status metrics are not available for additional interpretation. With few years’ data available to assess the status of this CU, annual monitoring should be prioritized, but caution should be used if interpreting improvements in the status until a longer time series is available.

The **Big Salmon CU** was assessed as *Amber* with *High* confidence. The recent generational average falls between the *absolute abundance* lower and upper thresholds, and falls above the *relative abundance* metric lower benchmark (20% S_{MSR}): 1370 (Node 22) (Figures 6-7; Table 7). This *Amber* WSP rapid status has been consistent throughout the time series. Although not used to assess WSP rapid status for this CU, the short-term trend (percent change) metric turned *Red* in the last three years. Therefore, this CU’s status should be tracked annually for potential shifts to *Red*.

The **Nordenskiold CU** was assessed as *Red* with *High* confidence. The recent generational average falls below the *absolute abundance* lower threshold: 1,500 (Node 3) (Figures 8-9; Table 8). This *Red* WSP rapid status has turned *Red* from *Amber* in the last three years, and a change between *Red* and *Amber* has occurred multiple times across the last two decades. Although not used to assess WSP rapid status for this CU, the short-term trend (percent change) metric has been *Red* for most of the past decade.

The **Pelly CU** was assessed as *Amber* with *High* confidence. The recent generational average falls between the *absolute abundance* lower and upper thresholds and falls above the *relative abundance* metric lower benchmark (20% S_{MSR}): 2,769 (Node 22) (Figures 10-11; Table 9). This *Amber* WSP rapid status has been generally consistent throughout the time series from 1995 to 2024. Although not used to assess WSP rapid status for this CU, the short-term trend (percent change) metric has been *Red* status

for the past three years. Therefore, this CU's status should be tracked annually for potential shifts to *Red*.

The **Middle Yukon River and Tributaries CU** was assessed as *Amber* with *High* confidence. The recent generational average falls between the *absolute abundance* lower and upper thresholds and falls above the *relative abundance* metric lower benchmark (20% S_{MSR}): 3,891 (Node 22) (Figures 12-13; Table 10). The WSP rapid status has varied between *Amber* and *Green* throughout the time series. Although not used to assess WSP rapid status for this CU, the short-term trend (percent change) metric has been in the *Amber* status zone for the past two years.

The **Stewart CU** was assessed as *Red* with *High* confidence. The recent generational average falls below the *absolute abundance* lower threshold: 1,500 (Node 3) (Figures 14-15; Table 11). This *Red* WSP rapid status has turned *Red* from *Amber* in the last two years, and most of the time series status was *Amber*. Although not used to assess WSP rapid status for this CU, the short-term trend (percent change) metric has been *Red* in the last two years.

The **White and Tributaries CU** was assessed as *Red* with *High* confidence. The recent generational average falls below the *absolute abundance* lower threshold: 1,500 (Node 3) (Figures 16-17; Table 12). This CU has been *Red* for the past two years and previously was *Amber*. Although not used to assess WSP rapid status for this CU, the short-term trend (percent change) metric has been *Red* for 14 years.

The **Northern Yukon River and Tributaries CU** was assessed as *Amber* with *Medium* confidence. The recent generational average falls between the *absolute abundance* lower and upper thresholds and falls just above the *relative abundance* metric lower benchmark (S_{MSR}): 1,609 (Node 22) (Figures 18-19; Table 13). Although not used to assess WSP rapid status for this CU, the short-term trend (percent change) metric has been *Red* for 13 years.

The **Salmon Fork CU** was assessed as *Data Deficient*. There are no available data on this CU.

The **Porcupine CU** was assessed as *Red* with *High* confidence. Data for this CU are combined with the Old Crow CU, as the assessment site is located in the Porcupine CU and downstream of the Old Crow CU and does not distinguish between Chinook salmon spawning upstream in each of the CUs. Although this time series could not be formally assessed with the WSP rapid status decision tree, the last four years of abundances fall below the absolute abundance threshold of 1,500 and the geometric mean which includes five of six most recent years with data is 695. When compared against the WSP rapid status decision tree, the generational average falls below the *absolute abundance* lower threshold: 1,500 (Node 3) (Figures 20-21; Table 14).

The **Old Crow CU** was assessed as *Red* with *High* confidence. Data for this CU are combined with the Porcupine CU, as an assessment site is located in the Porcupine CU and downstream of the Old Crow CU and does not distinguish between Chinook salmon spawning upstream in each of the CUs. Analysis of these data on aggregate for the CU indicate a *Red* status with *High* confidence for the Old Crow CU. When compared against the WSP rapid status decision tree, the generational average falls below the absolute abundance lower threshold: 1,500 (Node 3) (Figures 20-21; Table 14).

Context

Completion of the WSP status assessment is a Fish Stocks provisions requirement to inform the biological status of the Yukon Chinook SMU and Porcupine Chinook SMU through the assessment of the component CUs. Canadian-origin Yukon River Chinook salmon have been identified as a major stock, therefore triggering the necessity to assess the biological status of this stock in relation to CU specific limit reference points (LRP). LRP are assessed for SMUs, which can include one or more CUs (i.e., CUs are nested within SMUs). Using this approach, serious harm to a SMU is identified when any component CU status drops into the WSP *Red* zone. Under this definition, the CU status-LRP is '100% of CUs with statuses above *Red* status'. The implications are that if a single CU is the *Red* status zone, the SMU is assessed as being below its LRP, which in turn triggers a DFO rebuilding plan for the SMU.

Data

General background information on Chinook assessment projects in the Yukon River Basin can be found in Pestal et al. (2022). For most CUs, estimates of spawner abundance can be derived from a run-reconstruction model fit to genetic stock identification data from archived scale and tissue samples, estimates of daily and annual border passage of Chinook into the Yukon from Alaska, and estimates of Chinook harvest. This approach was first described in Connors et al. (2022) and has been updated and revised for the CSAS Research Document and Regional Peer Review occurring in June 2025. These run-reconstructions are based on observations from assessment projects that can be a relatively long distance from spawning grounds (e.g., 100s of kms) and do not account for any potential migration mortality that might occur over this distance. In addition to these run-reconstructions there are numerous tributary-scale estimates of spawner abundance that have been collected over the years via a variety of methods (e.g., sonar, aerial surveys, etc). In some cases, these tributary indices were considered to be the best available information to consider when assessing status. In other instances, the run reconstructions were deemed to offer the best, or only, available information upon which to assess status (Table 1).

Table 1. Conservation Units (CUs) included in this Stock Management Unit (SMU) and lists of the most abundant populations within each CU. *denotes which datasets are used in the WSP assessment.

CU No	CU name	Population data	Spawning Ground enumeration alternative method
Yukon Chinook CUs			
CK-68	Yukon River-Teslin Headwaters	<p>Expanded relative index of spawner abundance* based on Nisutlin (1969-2024; 11 gap years) and Wolf (1971-2024; 14 gap years) river aerial surveys that have assessed the same stream reaches over time. This expanded index accounts for years when only one of the two streams were surveyed by expanding based on the long-term average proportional contribution of the stream with an observation in a given year.</p> <p>As a sensitivity analysis, status was also assessed based on the genetics based run-reconstruction estimates of spawner abundance 1985-2024 and associated biological benchmarks.</p>	<p>Teslin mainstem below lake - sonar: 2013-2015</p> <p>Nisutlin - sonar: 2023-2024</p>
CK-69	Upper Yukon River	<p>Expanded absolute spawner abundance estimate* based on sum of Takhini sonar and Whitehorse fishway assessments in six of past eight years (2017-2024). The two recent years when the Takhini sonar was not operating (2019, 2020) were infilled based on the average proportional contribution of Takhini Chinook in years when there were data from both assessment projects.</p> <p>As a sensitivity analysis, status was also assessed based on the genetics based run-reconstruction estimates of spawner abundance 1985-2024 and associated biological benchmarks.</p>	<p>Whitehorse - fishway: 1961-2024</p> <p>Michie Creek - foot surveys: 2004-2024</p> <p>Takhini - aerial surveys: 1980, 1981, 1986-1988, 2017, 2018, 2020</p>
CK-70	Big Salmon	<p>Genetics based run-reconstruction estimates of absolute spawner abundance from 1985-2024, and associate biological benchmarks, that incorporate sonar based estimates of spawner abundance post-2005*. Reconstructions in non-sonar years are based on combined Middle Mainstem and Big Salmon CU run-reconstruction (with</p>	

		uncertainty), because genetics cannot reliably differentiate the two, and proportional contribution (with uncertainty/variability) of Big Salmon in years with sonar estimates.	
CK-71	Nordenskiold	Genetics based run-reconstruction estimates of absolute spawner abundance 1985-2024 and associated biological benchmarks*.	
CK-72	Pelly	Genetics based run-reconstruction estimates of absolute spawner abundance 1985-2024 and associated biological benchmarks*.	Blind Creek - weir: 1995-2018 (many gaps); sonar: 2016-2024 (gap in 2022)
CK-73	Middle Yukon River and Tributaries	Genetics based run-reconstruction estimates of absolute spawner abundance from 1985-2024, and associate biological benchmarks, that incorporate sonar based estimates of Big Salmon spawner abundance post 2005*. Reconstructions in non-sonar years are based on combined Middle Mainstem and Big Salmon CU run-reconstruction (with uncertainty), because genetics cannot reliably differentiate the two, and proportional contribution (with uncertainty/variability) of Middle Mainstem CU in years with Big Salmon sonar estimates.	Tatchun - visual (foot): 1970-1996; weir: 1996-2000 & 2021-2024
CK-74	Stewart	Genetics based run-reconstruction estimates of absolute spawner abundance 1985-2024 and associated biological benchmarks*. Includes post-hoc estimates of McQuesten River contribution to Northern Yukon CU which are then assigned to the Stewart CU.	
CK-75	White and Tributaries	Genetics based run-reconstruction estimates of absolute spawner abundance 1985-2024 and associated biological benchmarks*.	Tincup - aerial surveys: 1983-1998 (14 years)
CK-76	Northern Yukon River and Tributaries	Genetics based run-reconstruction estimates of absolute spawner abundance 1985-2024 and associated biological benchmarks*. Post-hoc estimates of McQuesten River contribution to CU were removed post-hoc and assigned to the Stewart CU.	Klondike - sonar: 2009-2011; 2020-2024 Chandindu - weir: 1998, 1999, 2003
Porcupine Chinook CUs			
CK-77	Salmon Fork	NA	NA

CK-78	Porcupine	NA	Porcupine River - sonar: 2014-2024 (gap in 2020); combined assessment of Chinook salmon from Porcupine and Old Crow CUs*
CK-79	Old Crow	NA	Porcupine River - sonar: 2014-2024 (gap in 2020); combined assessment of Chinook salmon from Porcupine and Old Crow CUs*

Table 2. Relative abundance-based benchmarks and credible intervals for each of the Yukon Chinook CUs for which spawner-recruitment models could be fit. The lower benchmark is 20% spawners at maximum recruitment (20% S_{MSR}) and the upper benchmark is 40% of S_{MSR} . The median (50% interval) are the values used in the decision tree. Benchmarks were estimated from models that assumed intrinsic productivity did not change over time.

CU #	CU name	20% S_{MSR} (median)	40% S_{MSR} (median)
CK-68	Yukon River-Teslin Headwaters	1,019	2,038
CK-69	Upper Yukon River	1,079	2,158
CK-70	Big Salmon	1,370	2,739
CK-71	Nordenskiold	319	638
CK-72	Pelly	2,769	5,539
CK-73	Middle Yukon River and Tributaries	3,891	7,782
CK-74	Stewart	796	1,592
CK-75	White and Tributaries	1,350	2,700
CK-76	Northern Yukon River and Tributaries	1,609	3,217
CK-77	Salmon Fork	NA	NA
CK-78	Porcupine	NA	NA
CK-79	Old Crow	NA	NA

WSP Rapid Status Summary

SMU LRP status based on WSP rapid status approaches (Pestal et al. 2023; DFO 2024):

The Yukon Chinook SMU falls below its CU-status based LRP, since five CUs are in the *Red* status zone; three with *High* confidence: Nordenskiöld (CK-71), Stewart (CK-74), and White (CK-75), and two with *Medium* confidence: Yukon River-Teslin Headwaters (CK-68) and Upper Yukon River (CK-69). The WSP rapid status for other CUs in this SMU are *Amber* with *High* confidence (CK-70, 72, 73) and *Medium* confidence (CK-76).

The Porcupine Chinook SMU falls below its CU-status based LRP, since two CUs are in the *Red* status zone with *High* confidence: Porcupine (CK-78) and Old Crow (CK-79). One other CU is *Data Deficient* (CK-77).

Yukon River-Teslin Headwaters

This CU contains the furthest migrating Yukon River Chinook salmon spawning populations. In the upper portion of the drainage, there are numerous spawning locations, with the Nisutlin River basin providing many sites with ideal spawning conditions. These are medium and small sized streams, with many lake headed systems. The lower section of the CU is the mainstem Teslin River, downstream of Teslin Lake. This is a large river and supports a relatively large Chinook salmon spawning population. The ecology between these two areas of the CU is unique, and current genetic tools are unable to differentiate mainstem Teslin River spawners from the Middle Yukon River and Tributaries CU. As a result, redrawing the border of the Yukon River-Teslin Headwaters CU to exclude the mainstem Teslin River below Teslin Lake should be given some consideration. Despite the ecological and genetic evidence that spawning populations below Teslin Lake are more similar to the Middle Yukon River and tributaries CU, for the purposes of this assessment we proceed with the current official CU boundary that extends to the mouth of the Teslin River in the Yukon River-Teslin Headwaters CU. However, we note that since the run-reconstruction estimates for the Yukon River-Teslin Headwaters CU are unable to account for spawning populations downstream of Teslin Lake they are aligned with the delineation of the Teslin system that local experts believe to be the most appropriate and recommend moving forward.

Local observations and aerial surveys over the past several decades suggest populations in this CU have fallen to extremely low abundances in recent years. Where many hundreds of fish were once observed, there are now dozens of fish appearing each year and in some instances, no fish. Additionally, some of these Chinook are the longest migrating in the Yukon River and current data and knowledge are unable to quantify en-route mortality of these fish once they pass the Eagle sonar site – the source of data for the run-reconstruction model. It may therefore be reasonable to conclude that Chinook in this CU are more prone to experience mortality within Canada, compared with most other CUs, which could reduce the observed returns compared to the run-reconstruction based estimates of returns.

A status assessment based on run-reconstruction estimates of total spawner abundance was completed for this CU (Appendix B). However, due to local observations, the availability of a long-term aerial dataset, and expert feedback which conflicted with the run-reconstruction based WSP status, it was determined that status should be assessed based on the tributary level long-term aerial dataset. Gaps in aerial data in recent years limited the ability of the rapid status algorithm to consider recent trends in abundance but did allow the recent generation index of spawning abundance to be compared to the long-term average and resulted in a recent year's status being assigned *Red* with *Medium* confidence. This status aligns with expert feedback and is therefore considered a more accurate representation of what is being seen on the ground than status based on the run-reconstruction model.

Upper Yukon River

This CU encompasses the most upstream portion of the Yukon River. Construction of a hydropower dam was completed on the Yukon River in Whitehorse in 1958. One year later, a fish ladder was constructed to allow returning adult Chinook salmon to reach their spawning habitats upstream of the dam. Since 1961, Chinook passage of the fish ladder has been recorded and in recent years, a sonar has estimated passage on the Takhini River since 2017 (absent 2019–2020). A small hatchery near the dam has been collecting brood stock at the fish ladder, and a hatchery component of returning Chinook has been documented since 1988.

Chinook above the dam face two key pressures that are unique in the Yukon Chinook SMU. Returning adults have to find and navigate through the longest wooden fish ladder in the world to pass the dam and access their spawning grounds, and previous telemetry and carcass survey assessments provide evidence that many fish attempt but fail to successfully use the ladder (Twardek et al. 2023a). Downstream migrating juveniles and smolts are also impeded by the dam, passing through a spillway or turbines, with recent indications suggesting 30% mortality of these fish (Twardek et al. 2023b).

Chinook migrating upstream of the dam primarily spawn in Michie Creek, a tributary of the M'Clintock River. Families would dry and smoke salmon along the banks of the M'Clintock River, and some caches of dried salmon were large enough to last through winter (Herkes 2015). In 1957, the chief biologist for the Pacific Area wrote to the deputy minister of Fisheries that “as many as 10,000 spring salmon were taken in the M'Clintock River some years ago” (Cox 1997). Similarly, a fishery officer recorded that as many as 25 families once harvested 300–400 fish each there, based on an interview with Johnny Joe (Cox 1997). Spawning ground surveys have been led by Kwanlin Dün First Nation in the upper reaches of Michie Creek since 2001, providing an important index of abundance in this CU (Jessup and de Graff 2024).

A status assessment based on run-reconstruction estimates of total spawner abundances was completed for this CU (Appendix B). However, due to local observations, the availability of recent tributary assessment projects that are believed to assess the majority of the CU, and expert feedback which conflicted with the run-reconstruction based WSP status, it was determined that status should be assessed based on the tributary level assessment projects and associated data.

Contemporary spawning in Lake Laberge tributaries which were historically utilized is not monitored and believed to be nil. It is unknown how much mainstem Yukon River spawning occurs, if any, below the dam and the portion of the CU below Lake Laberge. Therefore, it is assumed that nearly all Chinook salmon returning to this CU are assessed at the fish ladder and Takhini sonar and these data could be used to inform the *absolute abundance* metric. Based on the years when there are estimates from both systems, the Takhini makes up 50–80% of total spawners each year and 80–90% when removing the hatchery component from the fishway's annual return. These data were used to evaluate WSP status based on *absolute abundance* thresholds, and the CU is assessed as *Red* with *Medium* confidence.

While there is some uncertainty about whether this is truly an absolute abundance estimate, given the recent generational average of 818 and all else being equal, the two assessment projects (Takhini sonar and Whitehorse fishway) would have to index less than ~55% of total spawners in the CU for the absolute abundance threshold to not be met over the most recent generation. This is deemed to be highly unlikely given current knowledge of spawning distribution in the CU (Brown et al. 2017).

Big Salmon

This CU spans a relatively small geographic area, marginally larger than the Nordenskiöld CU. However, a sonar program has operated on the Big Salmon River since 2005 (gap in 2022), providing one of the

longer duration tributary abundance estimates of Chinook salmon in the SMU. This CU is *Amber*, however, the short-term trend metric turned *Red* in 2022 and is approaching *Red* with the *relative abundance* metric, so annual tracking is recommended.

Chinook of this CU are genetically indistinguishable from Chinook from the Middle Yukon River and Tributaries CU. However, the biogeography of this CU is unique and justifies its continued separation from other CUs.

The run reconstruction-based estimates of spawner abundance for this CU uses sonar assessment data since 2005, and for pre-2005 Big Salmon spawner abundance was assumed to be a fraction (with uncertainty) of the combined reconstructed Middle Yukon River and Tributaries and Big Salmon CUs, because of the inability to distinguish fish from the two CUs genetically. The resulting reconstructions of spawner abundance explicitly account for variability in the proportional contribution of the Big Salmon CU since the sonar has been in operation and uncertainty in combined reconstructed Middle Yukon River and Tributaries and Big Salmon CU spawner abundances, but assume that the proportional contribution of spawners to each CU has remained stable over time.

Nordenskiold

This CU is the smallest within the Yukon Chinook SMU. Beaver activity is significant in the CU, and beaver dams have remained more intact since the 1980s/90s due to reduced human presence on the river. This activity is believed to have limited Chinook salmon access to rearing and spawning habitats, which is only improved in years with high water levels. Beaver dams on Klusha Creek, a tributary of the Nordenskiold River, have been observed to prevent Chinook salmon access to spawning habitat. There have been projects focused on the removal of beaver dams, but renewed access to spawning habitats have been impeded by very low water levels.

Pelly

The Pelly CU is among the most abundance Chinook CU in the Yukon Chinook SMU. The geographic extent of spawning in the CU covers an area nearly as large as the Stewart CU, making it the second largest in the SMU, even though it's believed that the spawning habitat and populations are spread among the many tributaries and no single area holds a large component of the aggregate. Considering the large size of the CU, where spawning habitats may be separated by hundreds of kilometers of streams, recolonization of depleted or locally extirpated populations within the CU may be very slow or unrealized. The Pelly River is also the warmest tributary in the Yukon SMU (Shaftel et al. in review), and Chinook salmon returning to the spawning streams in the upper Pelly River system are among the furthest migrating in the Yukon River. These are two important characteristics of this CU which make these fish more vulnerable to potential en-route mortality.

Middle Yukon River and Tributaries

This CU contains a large section of the mainstem Yukon River in the central portion of the SMU, along with some culturally and biologically significant tributary spawning population (e.g., Tatchun Creek and Little Salmon River). Assessment on the tributaries has included approximately 40 years of aerial surveys on the Little Salmon River (ending in 2011), and surveys on Tatchun Creek over the same period which have been recently renewed. Assessment in the mainstem Yukon River is logistically challenging and has not been done. Without assessment that targets the mainstem spawning populations, it is critical to continue tributary level monitoring. The present approach is to monitor Chinook salmon at the CU level, until Tatchun Creek data is successfully evaluated against informing at this scale. Continued management and monitoring at the CU scale may not adequately detect differing or potentially

worsening trends in the smaller tributary spawning populations and therefore could result in losses in biological diversity within the CU and the aggregate SMU.

It is believed that this CU is the most abundant in the SMU, but existing reconstructions are convoluted and biased high. Genetic assignment suggests over 50% of Chinook in the SMU belong to this CU, however, current genetic baselines are unable to distinguish Chinook from this CU and the Big Salmon River and the mainstem Teslin River, two relatively large populations. Whereas run-reconstruction modeled results are able to account for and omit the Big Salmon component via sonar estimates, the mainstem Teslin River portion remains to bias the *relative abundance* estimate of this CU high. Despite these limitations in the data, it is believed that the WSP status of *Amber* status is accurate.

Stewart

This is the largest CU by area in the Yukon Chinook SMU, however, it is one of the least productive relative to area, with an average reconstructed spawner abundance of ~2,600 in recent generations.

The low productivity in this CU is partly due to a partial barrier, Fraser Falls, about 150 km upstream of its confluence with the Yukon River. The ability of Chinook to migrate past Fraser Falls is not well understood and neither are the impacts this has on the distribution of spawners each year, though spawning habitat is utilized upstream of the falls. Local observations suggest that natural eroding and the release of rocks may have improved passage condition in more recent years. With reduced body size of returning Canadian Yukon River Chinook salmon over time, it is also possible that there has been a decline in the number of returning adult Chinook with the strength to migrate past the falls.

There is a complex of hydrological and control structure dams on the Mayo River which have obstructed fish passage in this system since 1951. Traditional knowledge indicates that the historic Chinook salmon run size on the Mayo River was 1,000 to 2,000 fish. In recent years, aerial surveys on the lower Mayo River below the dam have estimated the small spawning population that remains. Renewed efforts by the First Nation of Na-cho Nyäk Dun are focused on enabling fish passage past the dams so they can return to the high quality habitat between the dams and in the upper Mayo Lake region.

Overall, there is a lack of local knowledge in recent generations on Chinook salmon of the Stewart CU due to the decline in returns and the declines/absence of fishing, however historic local and traditional knowledge is rich.

White and Tributaries

Monitoring and assessment of Chinook salmon in this CU has been less common compared to others, especially in the past 25 years. This is partly caused by the difficulty of accessing habitats used by Chinook salmon in this area, and the heavy silt loads that flow through the White River basin. Aerial surveys of Tincup Creek took place between 1983–1998, averaging over 100 Chinook annually. A radio tagging study in the early 2000s tracked adults to two main spawning streams in this CU, Nisling River and Tincup Creek. The Nisling River consistently held a relatively large component of the tagged Chinook salmon, typically in the lower portion of the river, but in some instances ~100km upstream of its mouth (Mercer and Eiler 2004). More recently, Kluane First Nation and radio telemetry results verified the presence of Chinook in Tincup Creek.

Hydrological changes to the Kluane Lake and River system are believed to have impacted Chum salmon habitats, and it is presumed that these same changes would be felt by Chinook salmon, if they are using the Kluane system. Chinook tagging studies completed over the decades have failed to identify tagged Chinook in the Kluane River.

Northern Yukon River and Tributaries

This CU is the most downstream region of the Yukon Chinook SMU. It is believed that the abundance of Chinook salmon in this CU will always remain below 10,000 and therefore, never achieve a *Green* status. This is a result of there being low habitat capacity among the few tributary systems available to Chinook salmon in this CU. Productivity is further reduced by having very low water temperatures in some of the spawning tributaries, the lowest in the SMU (Shaftel et al. in review), and the extensive impact that placer mining has had in the geographic extent of this CU.

Porcupine

This CU belongs to the Porcupine Chinook SMU in northern Yukon. Data for this CU are combined with the Old Crow CU, as the assessment site is located in the Porcupine CU and downstream of the Old Crow CU and does not distinguish between Chinook salmon spawning upstream in each of the CUs. Assessment of Chinook salmon began in 2014, and with a gap in 2020, there isn't a complete picture for the most recent generation. Therefore, the dataset is insufficient for formal assessment against the WSP status assessment framework. However, Chinook salmon abundance has declined to very low numbers the past few years, and the geometric mean from five of six most recent years with data is 695 which is well below the 1,500 fish absolute abundance threshold used to assess CUs as *Red*. In order to be assessed a status other than *Red*, the 2020 return to the Porcupine CU would have to be at least 70,000 to achieve a generational geometric mean greater than 1,500, which is exceptionally unlikely. Due to this extraordinary requirement, there is *High* confidence in assigning a *Red* status.

Old Crow

This CU is in the Porcupine Chinook SMU and is the most northern Chinook salmon CU in Yukon. Data for this CU are combined with the Porcupine CU, as an assessment site is located in the Porcupine CU and downstream of the Old Crow CU and does not distinguish between Chinook salmon spawning upstream in each of the CUs. Analysis of these data on aggregate for the Porcupine CU indicate a *Red* status with *High* confidence.

There is very limited data specific to Chinook in this CU or records of Chinook within its boundaries. A multi-year tagging study detected the presence of two tagged Chinook in this CU in 2003 and 2004. Additionally, traditional knowledge confirms the presence of Chinook in the CU (Anderton and Frost 2002), though no formal records capture the abundance or other characteristics of this population.

Salmon Fork

This CU is in the Porcupine Chinook SMU in northern Yukon and is the smallest Chinook salmon CU in Yukon. This CU is assigned *Data Deficient* based on the absence of data on this population. The Salmon Fork River is a tributary of the Black River, with approximately half of its basin being within Canada. Few records exist of Chinook salmon presence in this CU, but include detections of tagged Chinook salmon in the early 2000s and more recently in 2016, observation of Chinook salmon in the U.S. section of the Salmon Fork River. Until dedicated effort is made to monitor Chinook salmon in this CU, no further assessment can be made.

Future work

Currently four CUs are in the *Amber* status zone, however, given the recent declining trends in the Big Salmon (CK-70), Pelly (CK-72), and Northern (CK-75) CUs, these three CUs should be tracked annually to detect any deterioration in status.

The genetic baseline for Canadian-origin Yukon Chinook salmon should be improved to address current gaps and to increase sample sizes from areas with fewer samples in the baseline. An example of an area

which is currently not represented by spawning Chinook salmon samples in the baseline is a section of the mainstem Yukon River downstream of Lake Laberge, which covers a portion of the Upper Yukon River CU and the Middle Yukon River and Tributaries CU.

Status assessment would improve with increased CU level spawner data. Currently, three CUs in the Yukon Chinook SMU have no directed assessment on Chinook salmon (Stewart, Nordenskiold, and White and Tributaries) and two CUs in the Porcupine Chinook SMU have no current or directed assessment projects (Old Crow and Salmon Fork). Further, increasing the collection of consistent tributary level data within all the CUs could help to inform a more accurate biological status of corresponding CUs and the SMUs, and allow for more timely recognition in changes in status.

Table 3. Summary of the WSP rapid statuses for each CU within the Yukon Chinook and Porcupine Chinook SMUs. Statuses are indicated by colour and letter: *A: Amber; R: Red; and DD: Data Deficient.* *Asterisks denotes CUs where short-term trend metrics (percent change) are *Red*, indicating these CUs should be monitored annually for shifts in their overall status to *Red*. The status confidence levels assigned in this table are based on the expert review and discussion that took place as part of the assessment process and do not necessarily match the formal confidence levels determined by data input used in the rapid status algorithm.

CU #	#68	#69	#70	#71	#72	#73	#74	#75	#76	#77	#78	#79
CU name	Yukon River-Teslin Headwaters	Upper Yukon River	Big Salmon	Nordenskiold	Pelly	Middle Yukon River & Tributaries	Stewart	White & Tribs	Northern Yukon & Tributaries	Salmon Fork	Porcupine	Old Crow
WSP Rapid Status	R	R	A*	R	A*	A	R	R	A	DD	R	R
Status Confidence	Med	Med	High	High	High	High	High	High	Med	NA	High	High

Figure 1. Yukon Chinook WSP rapid statuses for years with applicable data. Each row summarizes the rapid statuses available for each CU. The asterisks denote statuses that were not based on formal application of WSP status decision tree due to data limitations.

Table 4. WSP rapid statuses for Yukon Chinook in 2024: The WSP rapid status algorithm was used to assess annual statuses for each Yukon CU. Background in Pestal et al. (2023) and DFO (2024) on WSP rapid status methods. Note the average generation length for each of these CUs is six years. *Asterisks denotes CUs where short-term trend metrics (percent change) are *Red*, indicating these CUs should be monitored annually for shifts in their overall status to *Red*.

CU #	CU Name	WSP Rapid Status (2024)	WSP rapid status node
CK-68	Yukon River-Teslin Headwaters	Red-Medium	The current year's (2024) WSP rapid status is <i>Red</i> with <i>Medium</i> confidence. The recent generational average of the expanded tributary index is 20% of the long-term average (Node 17) (Figures 2-3; Table 5).
CK-69	Upper Yukon River	Red-Medium	The current year's (2024) WSP rapid status is <i>Red</i> with <i>Medium</i> confidence. The recent generational average spawner abundance falls below the <i>absolute abundance</i> lower thresholds (1,500) (Node 3) (Figures 4-5; Table 6).
CK-70	Big Salmon	Amber-High*	The current year's (2024) WSP rapid status is <i>Amber</i> with <i>High</i> confidence. The recent generational average falls between the <i>absolute abundance</i> lower and upper thresholds, and falls above the <i>relative abundance</i> metric lower benchmark (20% S_{MSR}): 1,370 (Node 22) (Figures 6-7; Table 7). This <i>Amber</i> WSP rapid status has been consistent throughout the time series. *Although not used to assess WSP rapid status for this CU, the short-term trend (percent change) metric turned <i>Red</i> in the last two years. Therefore, this CU's status should be tracked annually for potential shifts to <i>Red</i> .
CK-71	Nordenskiöld	Red-High	The current year's (2024) WSP rapid status is <i>Red</i> with <i>High</i> confidence. The recent generational average falls below the <i>absolute abundance</i> lower thresholds (1,500) (Node 3) (Figures 8-9; Table 8). This <i>Red</i> WSP rapid status has turned <i>Red</i> from <i>Amber</i> in the last three years. *Although not used to assess WSP rapid status for this CU, the short-term trend (percent change) metric has been <i>Red</i> for most of the past decade.
CK-72	Pelly	Amber-High*	The current year's (2024) WSP rapid status is <i>Amber</i> with <i>High</i> confidence. The recent generational average falls between the <i>absolute abundance</i> lower and upper thresholds, and falls above the <i>relative abundance</i> metric lower benchmark (20% S_{MSR}): 2,769 (Node 22) (Figures 10-11; Table 9). This <i>Amber</i> WSP rapid status has been consistent throughout the time series from 1995 to 2024. *Although not used to assess WSP rapid status for this CU, the short-term trend (percent change) metric has been <i>Red</i> status for the past three years. Therefore, this CU's status should be tracked annually for potential shifts to <i>Red</i> .

CK-73	Middle Yukon River and Tributaries	Amber-High*	The current year's (2024) WSP rapid status is <i>Amber</i> with <i>High</i> confidence. The recent generational average falls between the <i>absolute abundance</i> lower and upper thresholds, and falls above the <i>relative abundance</i> metric lower benchmark (20% S_{MSR}): 3,891 (Node 22) (Figures 12-13; Table 10). The WSP rapid status has varied between <i>Amber</i> and <i>Green</i> throughout the time series. *Although not used to assess WSP rapid status for this CU, the short-term trend (percent change) metric has been in the <i>Amber</i> status zone for the past two years.
CK-74	Stewart	Red-High	The current year's (2024) WSP rapid status is <i>Red</i> with <i>High</i> confidence. The recent generational average falls below the <i>absolute abundance</i> lower thresholds (1,500) (Node 3) (Figures 14-15; Table 11). This <i>Red</i> WSP rapid status has turned <i>Red</i> from <i>Amber</i> in the last three years, and most of the time series status was <i>Amber</i> . *Although not used to assess WSP rapid status for this CU, the short-term trend (percent change) metric has been in the <i>Red</i> status zone for the past two years.
CK-75	White and Tributaries	Red-High	The current year's (2024) WSP rapid status is <i>Red</i> with <i>High</i> confidence. The recent generational average falls below the <i>absolute abundance</i> lower thresholds: 1,500 (Node 3) (Figures 16-17; Table 12). This CU has been <i>Red</i> for the past three years, and previously was <i>Amber</i> . *Although not used to assess WSP rapid status for this CU, the short-term trend (percent change) metric has been <i>Red</i> for the past 14 years.
CK-76	Northern Yukon River and Tributaries	Amber-Medium*	The current year's (2024) WSP rapid status is <i>Amber</i> with <i>Medium</i> confidence. The recent generational average falls between the <i>absolute abundance</i> lower and upper thresholds, and falls just above the <i>relative abundance</i> metric lower benchmark (S_{MSR}): 1,609 (Node 23) (Figures 18-19; Table 13). *Although not used to assess WSP rapid status for this CU, the short-term trend (percent change) metric has been <i>Red</i> for the past 13 years.
CK-77	Salmon Fork	Data Deficient	NA
CK-78	Porcupine	Red-High	Data used for this assessment is aggregated for both the Porcupine and Old Crow CUs. Although this time series could not be formally assessed with the WSP rapid status decision tree, the last four years of abundances fall below the <i>absolute abundance</i> threshold of 1,500 and the geometric mean which includes five of six most recent years with data is 695 (Figure 20). Though this is not a complete assessment since it requires comparing a complete generational average abundance to these thresholds, which was not possible given the data gap, analyses indicate this CU is assessed as <i>Red</i> status with

			<p><i>High</i> confidence. When compared against the WSP rapid status decision tree, the generational average falls below the absolute abundance lower threshold: 1,500 (Node 3) (Figures 20-21; Table 14).</p>
CK-79	Old Crow	Red-High	<p>The current year's (2024) WSP rapid status is <i>Red</i> with <i>High</i> confidence. Data for this CU are combined with the Porcupine CU. Analysis of these data on aggregate for the Porcupine CU indicate the last four years of abundances fall below the <i>absolute abundance</i> threshold of 1,500 and the geometric mean which includes five of six most recent years with data is 695 (Figure 20). Though this is not a complete assessment since it requires comparing a complete generational average abundance to these thresholds, which was not possible given the data gap, analyses indicate this CU is assessed in the <i>Red</i> status with <i>High</i> confidence. When compared against the WSP rapid status decision tree, the generational average falls below the absolute abundance lower threshold: 1,500 (Node 3) (Figures 20-21; Table 14).</p>

Figure 3. Algorithm pathway taken to assess status for Yukon River-Teslin Headwaters (CK-68, Yukon) in 2024. See table below.

Table 5: Decision tree path given data and metric values for Yukon River-Teslin Headwaters (CK-68, Yukon). For each node, the algorithm decision is made by comparing the CUs current metric value to the metric threshold and answering Yes or No, running through sequential nodes and decisions until the final WSP rapid status for that CU and year is reached.

Node	Metric	CUs current value	Metric Threshold	Algorithm Decision
1	absolute abundance	NA (does not apply)	Absolute abundance metric not used	NO
2	absolute abundance	NA (does not apply)	Absolute abundance metric not used	NO
4	relative abundance	NA (does not apply)	Relative abundance metric not used	NO
8	current generation index of abundance less than long-term average	82 (20% of long-term average of 410)	Less than 79% of long-term average	YES
17	FINAL STATUS NODE			Red

CK-69 Upper Yukon River

Figure 4: Metrics and Status for Upper Yukon River (CK-69, Yukon). Panels on top show the four standard WSP metrics, calculated based on the available time series of spawner abundances. Bottom panel summarizes the status for each individual metric and shows the resulting rapid status for the CU with a confidence rating.

Figure 5. Algorithm pathway taken to assess status for Upper Yukon River (CK-69, Yukon) in 2024. See table below.

Table 6: Decision tree path given data and metric values for Upper Yukon River (CK-69, Yukon). For each node, the algorithm decision is made by comparing the CUs current metric value to the metric threshold and answering Yes or No, running through sequential nodes and decisions until the final WSP rapid status for that CU and year is reached.

Node	Metric	CUs current value	Metric Threshold	Algorithm Decision
1	absolute abundance	818	Less than 1,500	YES
3	FINAL STATUS NODE			Red

CK-70 Big Salmon

Figure 6: Metrics and Status for Big Salmon (CK-70, Yukon). Panels on top show the four standard WSP metrics, calculated based on the available time series of spawner abundances. Bottom panel summarizes the status for each individual metric and shows the resulting rapid status for the CU with a confidence rating.

Figure 7. Algorithm pathway taken to assess status for Big Salmon (CK-70, Yukon) in 2024. See table below.

Table 7: Decision tree path given data and metric values for Big Salmon (CK-70, Yukon). For each node, the algorithm decision is made by comparing the CUs current metric value to the metric threshold and answering Yes or No, running through sequential nodes and decisions until the final WSP rapid status for that CU and year is reached.

Node	Metric	CUs current value	Metric Threshold	Algorithm Decision
1	absolute abundance	2,091	Less than 1,500	NO
2	absolute abundance	2,091	Less than 10,000	YES
5	relative abundance	YES	NA	YES
11	relative abundance: < lower BM	2,091	1,370	NO
22	FINAL STATUS NODE			Amber

CK-71 Nordenskiöld

Figure 8: Metrics and Status for Nordenskiöld (CK-71, Yukon). Panels on top show the four standard WSP metrics, calculated based on the available time series of spawner abundances. Bottom panel summarizes the status for each individual metric and shows the resulting rapid status for the CU with a confidence rating.

Figure 9. Algorithm pathway taken to assess status for Nordenskiöld (CK-71, Yukon) in 2024. See table below.

Table 8: Decision tree path given data and metric values for Nordenskiöld (CK-71, Yukon). For each node, the algorithm decision is made by comparing the CUs current metric value to the metric threshold and answering Yes or No, running through sequential nodes and decisions until the final WSP rapid status for that CU and year is reached.

Node	Metric	CUs current value	Metric Threshold	Algorithm Decision
1	absolute abundance	1,176	Less than 1,500	YES
3	FINAL STATUS NODE			Red

Figure 10: Metrics and Status for Pelly (CK-72, Yukon). Panels on top show the four standard WSP metrics, calculated based on the available time series of spawner abundances. Bottom panel summarizes the status for each individual metric and shows the resulting rapid status for the CU with a confidence rating.

Figure 11. Algorithm pathway taken to assess status for Pelly (CK-72, Yukon) in 2024. See table below.

Table 9: Decision tree path given data and metric values for Pelly (CK-72, Yukon). For each node, the algorithm decision is made by comparing the CUs current metric value to the metric threshold and answering Yes or No, running through sequential nodes and decisions until the final WSP rapid status for that CU and year is reached.

Node	Metric	CUs current value	Metric Threshold	Algorithm Decision
1	absolute abundance	2,847	Less than 1,500	NO
2	absolute abundance	2,847	Less than 10,000	YES
5	relative abundance	YES	NA	YES
11	relative abundance: < lower BM	2,847	2,769	NO
22	FINAL STATUS NODE			Amber

CK-73 Middle Yukon River and Tributaries

Figure 12: Metrics and Status for Middle Yukon River and Tributaries (CK-73, Yukon). Panels on top show the four standard WSP metrics, calculated based on the available time series of spawner abundances. Bottom panel summarizes the status for each individual metric and shows the resulting rapid status for the CU with a confidence rating.

Figure 13. Algorithm pathway taken to assess status for Middle Yukon River and Tributaries (CK-73, Yukon) in 2024. See table below.

Table 10: Decision tree path given data and metric values for Middle Yukon River and Tributaries (CK-73, Yukon). For each node, the algorithm decision is made by comparing the CUs current metric value to the metric threshold and answering Yes or No, running through sequential nodes and decisions until the final WSP rapid status for that CU and year is reached.

Node	Metric	CUs current value	Metric Threshold	Algorithm Decision
1	absolute abundance	5,712	Less than 1,500	NO
2	absolute abundance	5,712	Less than 10,000	YES
5	relative abundance	YES	NA	YES
11	relative abundance: < lower BM	5,712	3,891	NO
22	FINAL STATUS NODE			Amber

CK-74 Stewart

Figure 14: Metrics and Status for Stewart (CK-74, Yukon). Panels on top show the four standard WSP metrics, calculated based on the available time series of spawner abundances. Bottom panel summarizes the status for each individual metric and shows the resulting rapid status for the CU with a confidence rating.

Figure 15. Algorithm pathway taken to assess status for Stewart (CK-74, Yukon) in 2024. See table below.

Table 11: Decision tree path given data and metric values for Stewart (CK-74, Yukon). For each node, the algorithm decision is made by comparing the CUs current metric value to the metric threshold and answering Yes or No, running through sequential nodes and decisions until the final WSP rapid status for that CU and year is reached.

Node	Metric	CUs current value	Metric Threshold	Algorithm Decision
1	absolute abundance	1,355	Less than 1,500	YES
3	FINAL STATUS NODE			Red

CK-75 White and Tributaries

Figure 16: Metrics and Status for White and Tributaries (CK-75, Yukon). Panels on top show the four standard WSP metrics, calculated based on the available time series of spawner abundances. Bottom panel summarizes the status for each individual metric and shows the resulting rapid status for the CU with a confidence rating.

Figure 17. Algorithm pathway taken to assess status for White and Tributaries (CK-75, Yukon) in 2024. See table below.

Table 12: Decision tree path given data and metric values for White and Tributaries (CK-75, Yukon). For each node, the algorithm decision is made by comparing the CUs current metric value to the metric threshold and answering Yes or No, running through sequential nodes and decisions until the final WSP rapid status for that CU and year is reached.

Node	Metric	CUs current value	Metric Threshold	Algorithm Decision
1	absolute abundance	1,182	Less than 1,500	YES
3	FINAL STATUS NODE			Red

CK-76 Northern Yukon River and Tributaries

Figure 18: Metrics and Status for Northern Yukon River and Tributaries (CK-76, Yukon). Panels on top show the four standard WSP metrics, calculated based on the available time series of spawner abundances. Bottom panel summarizes the status for each individual metric and shows the resulting rapid status for the CU with a confidence rating.

Figure 19. Algorithm pathway taken to assess status for Northern Yukon River and Tributaries (CK-76, Yukon). See table below.

Table 13: Decision tree path given data and metric values for Northern Yukon River and Tributaries (CK-76, Yukon). For each node, the algorithm decision is made by comparing the CUs current metric value to the metric threshold and answering Yes or No, running through sequential nodes and decisions until the final WSP rapid status for that CU and year is reached.

Node	Metric	CUs current value	Metric Threshold	Algorithm Decision
1	absolute abundance	1,735	Less than 1,500	NO
2	absolute abundance	1,735	Less than 10,000	YES
5	relative abundance	YES	NA	YES
11	relative abundance: < lower BM	1,735	1,609	NO
22	FINAL STATUS NODE			Amber

CK-78 Porcupine and CK-79 Old Crow

Figure 20: Metrics and Status for Porcupine (CK-78, Porcupine) and Old Crow (CK-79, Porcupine). Panels on top show the four standard WSP metrics, calculated based on the available time series of spawner abundances. Bottom panel summarizes the status for each individual metric and shows the resulting rapid status for the CU with a confidence rating.

Figure 21. Algorithm pathway taken to assess status for Porcupine (CK-78, Porcupine) and Old Crow (CK-79, Porcupine). See table below.

Table 14: Decision tree path given data and metric values for Porcupine (CK-78, Porcupine) and Old Crow (CK-79, Porcupine). For each node, the algorithm decision is made by comparing the CUs current metric value to the metric threshold and answering Yes or No, running through sequential nodes and decisions until the final WSP rapid status for that CU and year is reached.

Node	Metric	CUs current value	Metric Threshold	Algorithm Decision
1	absolute abundance	695	Less than 1,500	YES
3	FINAL STATUS NODE			Red

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Appendix A

Wild Salmon Policy Rapid Status

Why did we develop a WSP rapid status assessment approach?

Canadian Pacific salmon abundances are broadly declining, and this is expected to continue under climate change. To track and manage these changes, it is increasingly important to have up-to-date assessments of the biological statuses for Pacific salmon Conservation Units (CUs), which represent the fundamental units of salmon biodiversity. Tracking salmon CU status is the first strategy of DFO's Wild Salmon Policy (WSP). The WSP recognized that there was a growing conservation ethic for Pacific salmon, one that recognizes the inherent value of salmon, the importance of diversity among and within populations, and the obvious and enduring cultural, social, and economic benefits. Existing WSP integrated status assessment processes only get us part-way there. Since they are labour and time intensive, they have been completed for 11% of the 377 Canadian Pacific salmon CUs and are 5–10 years out of date. The WSP rapid status assessment approach we developed enables us to assess status annually for CUs with applicable data.

What is a WSP rapid status assessment?

WSP rapid status assessments can assign a *Red* (poor), *Amber* (intermediate), or *Green* (good) status (Table A1), with a *Low*, *Medium*, or *High* confidence rating, to CUs with applicable data. These statuses are generated by a computer-coded WSP rapid status decision tree, which is applied to salmon CU data. A WSP rapid status decision tree is a set of decision rules that approximate the decision-making process that experts used in WSP integrated status assessments (Table A2; Figure A1). The algorithm assigns a WSP rapid status depending on answers to Yes/No questions for CU status data sets. The combination of metrics applied, and their individual status values compared to metric thresholds, leads to a final WSP rapid status.

How was the WSP rapid status assessment algorithm selected?

We developed a suite of candidate algorithms based on past WSP integrated assessments. We evaluated the performance across multiple candidate WSP rapid status algorithms, by comparing their respective rapid statuses against WSP integrated statuses assigned from past expert-driven processes. We selected the top-performing algorithm for use in future applications.

What are the three core principles of the WSP rapid status algorithm?

The first core principle is that WSP CUs were identified and WSP rapid statuses were developed based on conservation biology principles, and scientific peer-reviewed publications. This ensures that Pacific salmon statuses are scientifically objective, consistent, and comparable across BC/Yukon CUs. Standardized metrics also need to be widely applicable and relatively easy to use and update regularly. The second core principle of WSP rapid status assessment is the vetting of data and evaluation of WSP rapid statuses by experts on specific salmon CUs. The final core principle is continual learning and refinement.

How will we use the WSP rapid status algorithm?

The WSP rapid status algorithm is central to DFO's Salmon Scanner. This is an interactive data

visualization tool specifically designed for experts to support their work on Pacific salmon. This tool enables users to compare status trends across CUs and years to support scientific discovery, and decision-making processes. The Salmon Scanner will support status evaluations for SMUs against their limit reference points (LRP), which is a legal requirement under the modernized *Fisheries Act* (2019). Other applications could include state of the salmon reporting, and to support climate change vulnerability assessments. In these decision-making contexts, WSP rapid statuses would be combined with expert input and peer-review.

The algorithm sequence is as follows (see Figure A1; Table A2):

1. The first question is whether or not a CU has a current absolute abundance value, and if so, whether or not this value falls below the lower threshold of 1,500 (which adds a buffer to Committee on the Status of Endangered Wildlife in Canada's (COSEWIC) Criterion D1 for small population size of 1,000). If the answer to this question is Yes, then the CU is assigned *Red* (node 3), with *High* confidence.
2. If the answer to the first question is No, then the second question is whether or not the CU has a current absolute abundance value, and if so, whether or not the current abundance is below the upper threshold of 10,000, which is COSEWIC's Criterion C upper benchmark. This second question splits the decision nodes into two Pathways: Pathway 1 (No to this question) and Pathway 2 (Yes to this question).
 - **Pathway 1:** is where a CU either does not have a current absolute abundance value, or has these data, and it falls above the upper threshold for this metric. This pathway is split with the question: can this CU be assessed with a relative abundance metric. If the answer is Yes, a *Red* (node 19), *Amber* (node 37) or *Green* (node 36) WSP rapid status is assigned, with *High* confidence, depending on where the current abundance value falls relative to this metric's lower and upper thresholds. If the answer is NO, then comparisons are made between the CU's current abundances and percent change to thresholds for these metrics, which assign a *Red* with *Medium* confidence, or *Green* or *Amber* with *Low* confidence status.
 - **Pathway 2:** is where a CU has absolute abundance data, and these abundances fall between the lower and upper thresholds. In this pathway, absolute abundances restrict WSP rapid statuses to only *Amber* or *Red*. This pathway is split with the question: can this CU be assessed with a relative abundance metric. If the answer is Yes, an *Amber* (node 22) with *Medium* confidence, or *Red* (node 23) with *High* confidence is assigned, depending on whether the CU's current abundance value falls above the relative abundance metric lower threshold or below. If the CU cannot be assessed with a relative abundance metric, then it is compared to the lower threshold of the long-term trend metric and assigned *Amber* (node 20) with *Medium* confidence if above, or *Red* (node 21) with *Medium* confidence if below.

Table A1. Biological status zones under the Wild Salmon Policy (WSP).

Status	Definition
Red	Poor status CU facing an imminent threat of extinction [revised definition, given alignment with COSEWIC <i>Endangered</i> statuses]
Amber	“While a CU in the <i>Amber</i> zone should be at low risk of loss, there will be a degree of lost production. Still, this situation may results when CUs share risk factors with other, more productive units”. Aligns with COSEWIC <i>Threatened and Special Concern</i> statuses.
Green	“identif[ies] whether harvest are greater than the level expected to provide on an average annual basis, the maximum annual catch for a CU, given existing conditions...there would not be a high probability of losing the CU”. Aligns with COSEWIC <i>Not at Risk</i> statuses.
DD	Data deficient. CUs have been designated as DD if there is no data available, or if the available data is insufficient for calculating status metrics (after quality control).

Table A2. WSP rapid status *Learning Tree 3* status assignments by node (see Figure 1). This table presents the decisions in *Learning Tree 3* that led to *Red* or *Amber* or *Green* status assignments; status outcomes depend on the pathway and decisions made. The final node that corresponds to the status assignment is presented below (see Figure 1).

Node	Status	Rule
3	<i>Red</i>	Data Type is Absolute Abundance AND <i>Absolute Abundance</i> < 1,500
17	<i>Red</i>	Data Type is Relative Index OR <i>Absolute Abundance</i> ≥ 1,500; then Data Type is Relative Index OR <i>Absolute Abundance</i> ≥ 10,000; then no <i>Relative Abundance</i> lower benchmark; then <i>Long Term Trend</i> < 79%
19	<i>Red</i>	Data Type is Relative Index OR <i>Absolute Abundance</i> ≥ 1,500; then Data Type is Relative Index OR <i>Absolute Abundance</i> ≥ 10,000 then have <i>Relative Abundance</i> lower benchmark; then <i>Relative Abundance</i> < <i>Relative Abundance</i> lower benchmark
20	<i>Amber</i>	Data Type is Relative Index OR <i>Absolute Abundance</i> ≥ 1,500; then Data Type is Absolute Abundance AND <i>Absolute Abundance</i> <10,000; then no <i>Relative Abundance</i> lower benchmark; then <i>Long Term Trend</i> ≥ 79%
21	<i>Red</i>	Data Type is Relative Index OR <i>Absolute Abundance</i> ≥ 1,500; then Data Type is Absolute Abundance AND <i>Absolute Abundance</i> <10,000; then no <i>Relative Abundance</i> lower benchmark; then <i>Long Term Trend</i> < 79%
22	<i>Amber</i>	Data Type is Relative Index OR <i>Absolute Abundance</i> ≥ 1,500; then Data Type is Absolute Abundance AND <i>Absolute Abundance</i> <10,000; then have <i>Relative Abundance</i> lower benchmark; then <i>Relative Abundance</i> ≥ <i>Relative Abundance</i> lower benchmark
23	<i>Red</i>	Data Type is Relative Index OR <i>Absolute Abundance</i> ≥ 1,500; then Data Type is Absolute Abundance AND <i>Absolute Abundance</i> <10,000; then have <i>Relative Abundance</i> lower benchmark; then <i>Relative Abundance</i> < <i>Relative Abundance</i> lower benchmark

33	<i>Red</i>	Data Type is Relative Index OR <i>Absolute Abundance</i> $\geq 1,500$; then Data Type is Relative Index OR <i>Absolute Abundance</i> $\geq 10,000$; then no <i>Relative Abundance</i> lower benchmark; then <i>Long Term Trend</i> $\geq 79\%$; then Percent Change < -70
36	<i>Green</i>	Data Type is Relative Index OR <i>Absolute Abundance</i> $\geq 1,500$; then Data Type is Relative Index OR <i>Absolute Abundance</i> $\geq 10,000$ then have <i>Relative Abundance</i> lower benchmark; then <i>Relative Abundance</i> \geq <i>Relative Abundance</i> lower benchmark; then <i>Relative Abundance</i> \geq <i>Relative Abundance</i> upper benchmark x 1.1
37	<i>Amber</i>	Data Type is Relative Index OR <i>Absolute Abundance</i> $\geq 1,500$; then Data Type is Relative Index OR <i>Absolute Abundance</i> $\geq 10,000$ then have <i>Relative Abundance</i> lower benchmark; then <i>Relative Abundance</i> \geq <i>Relative Abundance</i> lower benchmark; then <i>Relative Abundance</i> $<$ <i>Relative Abundance</i> upper benchmark x 1.1
64	<i>Green</i>	Data Type is Relative Index OR <i>Absolute Abundance</i> $\geq 1,500$; then Data Type is Relative Index OR <i>Absolute Abundance</i> $\geq 10,000$; then no <i>Relative Abundance</i> lower benchmark; then <i>Long Term Trend</i> $\geq 79\%$; then Percent Change < -70 then <i>Long Term Trend</i> ≥ 233
65	<i>Amber</i>	Data Type is Relative Index OR <i>Absolute Abundance</i> $\geq 1,500$; then Data Type is Relative Index OR <i>Absolute Abundance</i> $\geq 10,000$; then no <i>Relative Abundance</i> lower benchmark; then <i>Long Term Trend</i> $\geq 79\%$; then Percent Change < -70 then <i>Long Term Trend</i> < 233

Figure A1. WSP rapid status algorithm (Table A2 includes written descriptions). To assess a CU, metric values are compared to thresholds presented at each decision point. Yes or No answers split each path of the decision tree, terminating at WSP rapid status assignments. The different splits are identified as nodes: 1 to 65. **Pathway 1** is taken when the CU has no absolute abundance data, or these data exist, but fall above its upper threshold of 10,000. **Pathway 2** is taken when the CU has absolute abundance data and these fall under its upper benchmark of 10,000. *High, Medium, or Low* confidence ratings are identified for each node.

run-reconstruction based estimates of spawner abundance through time. Panels on top show the four standard WSP metrics, calculated based on the available time series of spawner abundances. Bottom panel summarizes the status for each individual metric and shows the resulting rapid status for the CU with a confidence rating.

Figure B2. Algorithm pathway taken to assess status for Yukon River-Teslin Headwaters (CK-68, Yukon) in 2024, based on the use of run-reconstruction based estimates of spawner abundance through time. See table below.

Table B1: Decision tree path given data and metric values for Yukon River-Teslin Headwaters (CK-68, Yukon), based on the use of run-reconstruction based estimates of spawner abundance through time. For each node, the algorithm decision is made by comparing the CUs current metric value to the metric threshold and answering Yes or No, running through sequential nodes and decisions until the final WSP rapid status for that CU and year is reached.

Node	Metric	CUs current value	Metric Threshold	Algorithm Decision
1	absolute abundance	2,824	Less than 1,500	NO
2	absolute abundance	2,824	Less than 10,000	YES
5	relative abundance	YES	NA	YES
11	relative abundance: < lower BM	2,824	1,019	NO
22	FINAL STATUS NODE			Amber

CK-69 Upper Yukon River

Figure B3: Metrics and Status for Upper Yukon River (CK-69, Yukon), based on the use of run-reconstruction based estimates of spawner abundance through time. Panels on top show the four standard WSP metrics, calculated based on the available time series of spawner abundances. Bottom panel summarizes the status for each individual metric and shows the resulting rapid status for the CU with a confidence rating.

Figure B4. Algorithm pathway taken to assess status for Upper Yukon River (CK-69, Yukon) in 2024, based on the use of run-reconstruction based estimates of spawner abundance through time. See table below.

Table B2: Decision tree path given data and metric values for Upper Yukon River (CK-69, Yukon), based on the use of run-reconstruction based estimates of spawner abundance through time. For each node, the algorithm decision is made by comparing the CUs current metric value to the metric threshold and answering Yes or No, running through sequential nodes and decisions until the final WSP rapid status for that CU and year is reached.

Node	Metric	CUs current value	Metric Threshold	Algorithm Decision
1	absolute abundance	1,705	Less than 1,500	NO
2	absolute abundance	1,705	Less than 10,000	YES
5	relative abundance	YES	NA	YES
11	relative abundance: < lower BM	1,705	1,079	NO
22	FINAL STATUS NODE			Amber

Appendix C

WSP Salmon Scanner expert review workshops list of participants.

List of people (affiliations) who participated in expert review workshops, completed in spring 2025. Workshops were held to introduce and discuss the WSP Salmon Scanner and its results for Yukon River Chinook salmon CUs (both Yukon Chinook SMU and Porcupine Chinook SMU).

- Sue Grant (Fisheries and Oceans Canada) , workshop lead
- Adam O'Dell (Fisheries and Oceans Canada), workshop co-lead
- Stephanie Lyons (Yukon First Nation Salmon Stewardship Alliance/Council of Yukon First Nations)
- Sebastian Jones (Yukon Fish and Wildlife Management Board)
- Chris Burns (LGL Limited / Selkirk First Nation Representative)
- Karlie Knight (Tr'ondek Hwech'in First Nation)
- Wes Moir (Yukon First Nation Salmon Stewardship Alliance/Council of Yukon First Nations)
- Brendan Connors (Fisheries and Oceans Canada)
- Hannah Hunter (Fisheries and Oceans Canada)
- Marina Milligan (Yukon First Nation Salmon Stewardship Alliance/Council of Yukon First Nations)
- Elizabeth MacDonald (Yukon First Nation Salmon Stewardship Alliance/Council of Yukon First Nations)
- Mark Connor (Taku River Tlingit First Nation)
- Kim Koyczan (Ta'an Kwach'an Council)
- Ian Riemenschneider (Environmental Dynamics Inc.)
- Ben Schonewille (Environmental Dynamics Inc.)
- Taylor Bradley (Yukon Salmon Sub-Committee)
- Stephanie Peacock (Pacific Salmon Foundation)
- William Twardek (EcoFish Research Ltd., Kwanlin Dün First Nation Representative)
- Hannah Turner (Carcross/Tagish First Nation)
- Jeremy Brammer (Vuntut Gwitchin First Nation)
- Rebecca Freeman (Little Salmon Carmacks First Nation)
- Gottfried Pestal (SOLV Consulting Ltd.)
- Lars Jessup (First Nation of Na-Cho Nyäk Dun Representative)
- Gillian Rourke (Teslin Tlingit Council)
- Kate Andre (Ta'an Kwach'an Council)